

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Jin, W., Zhuge, J., & Wu, H. (2023). Research on the Influencing Factors and Countermeasures for the Effectiveness of Talent Training in School-enterprise Cooperation in Vocational Education-Taking Haining City as an Example. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 6(4), 194-201.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.06.04.455

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Research on the Influencing Factors and Countermeasures for the Effectiveness of Talent Training in School-enterprise Cooperation in Vocational Education-Taking Haining City as an Example

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Abstract

Currently, the effectiveness of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education is not significant, but effectiveness is an important indicator of the quality of technical personnel training. On the basis of survey and study, the factors affecting the effectiveness of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education are elaborated and analyzed from four perspectives: institutional level, colleges themselves, enterprise level and stakeholders. Based on this, four development suggestions are proposed, such as giving play to the leading role of the government in school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education, establishing and improving the institutional framework for school-enterprise cooperation with the effective participation of industry associations, strengthening the legalization of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education, and strengthening the degree of interest association between vocational education and cooperative enterprises. We hope to provide some reference for the high-quality development of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education.

Keywords: Vocational Education, School-Enterprise Cooperation, Effectiveness, Influencing Factors, Countermeasures And Suggestions

1. Introduction

The 18th, 19th and 20th National Congress of the Communist Party of China (CPC) successively pointed out that China should increase the development of human resources, train increasingly high-quality workers, train a group of top talent in enterprises, and provide strong support for the development of enterprises. To effectively guarantee human resources, we must turn from a large education country to a strong education country, and the goal of talent training must change from quantity to quality.

After entering the new era, Haining's industrial structure and economic development mode are facing major adjustments, and development has changed from factor-driven to innovation-driven. To meet the requirements of

industrial structure, economic development mode, and innovation drive, it is necessary to change the methods of talent training and reform the paths of talent training to cultivate more types of talent that are compatible with Haining's economic and social development. These types of talent include different levels, including specialized workers engaged in front-line production and leading talent and scientists engaged in technology research and development. The layout of industries has a great impact on the major setting of vocational education, which in turn affects the quantity and specifications of technical skills personnel trained. The quality and skills of the labor force in traditional enterprises are not high enough to meet the needs of Haining's economic, social and technological development. For better development, Haining enterprises are in urgent need of relevant skilled personnel, and they need to continuously improve the technical skills of the labor force and the knowledge and skill level of the enterprise labor force. The accelerated development of vocational education is one of the best ways to improve the technical skills of the enterprise labor force. The cultivation of technical skills personnel is inseparable from vocational education. There are relatively few scholars studying the effectiveness of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education, and the majority of studies are on school-enterprise cooperation mechanisms, models, and countermeasures. Some scholars have conducted empirical research on the effectiveness of school-enterprise cooperation from the perspective of satisfaction. The results show that there are six aspects that have a great impact on the satisfaction degree of school-enterprise cooperation, such as overall curriculum planning, internship performance assessment methods, and internship systems (Cui & Pan, 2020; Zhang J., 2020; Tang et al., 2014). At the same time, it is necessary to construct a performance model of vocational education school-enterprise cooperation and use the fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method to evaluate the three aspects of resources, process and effect (Ding, 2020). By referring to the research results of other countries, scholars have constructed a four-dimensional conceptual model of school-enterprise cooperation and studied the effectiveness of school-enterprise cooperation from the aspects of depth and breadth (Xu, 2017; Wu et al., 2015). Zhang et al. used the questionnaire method to study the satisfaction and enthusiasm of enterprises to participate in school-enterprise cooperation and showed that many enterprises are willing to accept vocational college students as internships and have high enthusiasm for participating in school-enterprise cooperation (Zhang P. & Nan, 2016).

From the overall situation, the school-enterprise cooperation for the integration of vocational education in Haining has increased in both scale and quality, but there is still some distance from the goal. Due to the complexity and variability of school-enterprise cooperation, there are still many unresolved issues in enterprise cooperation. Therefore, on the basis of investigation and research, this paper focused on the influencing factors and the development countermeasures and suggestions for the integration of school-enterprise cooperation in Haining's vocational education.

2. School-enterprise cooperation in vocational education Analysis of Factors Influencing Effectiveness

Currently School-enterprise cooperation in vocational education The final results of the effectiveness are not satisfactory, and the effect is not significant, but the effectiveness is an important indicator of the quality of technical personnel training. To improve the effectiveness of school-enterprise cooperation, it is necessary to analyze the factors that cause the insignificant effectiveness of the study. After interviewing, it was decided to elaborate and analyze from four perspectives: institutional level, institution itself, enterprise level, and stakeholders.

2.1 Analysis of influencing factors at the institutional level

The effectiveness of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education is positively proportional to the role of the government because school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education needs to create a favorable external environment. However, at present, there are still some problems in the school-enterprise cooperation system in Haining that have a direct impact on the effectiveness of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education. The purpose of the implementation mechanism is to strengthen the execution of the system, but at present, due to the imperfection of the institutional mechanisms, the implementation of the system is difficult and cannot be implemented well. In school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education, the school-enterprise generally has several cooperation partners. When communicating, they need to clearly understand the other

party's dynamics to conduct in-depth exchanges. However, in real life, there are basically no organizations that provide this kind of information service, and as a result, the quality of exchanges between the school and the enterprise is not high and is superficial. Each year in Haining, a large number of vocational education students enter the enterprise. They are different majors and work in different positions in the enterprise. To achieve high-quality practice in posts, careful planning and arrangement are needed, but this type of service organization and mechanism fail to provide such a solution. Create.

2.2 Analysis of influencing factors at the school level

Vocational colleges are an important factor in the promotion of school-enterprise cooperation, and the major development and talent training models of colleges and universities have a great impact on their effectiveness. The essence of the education and teaching innovation reform currently advocated is to change the mode of training talent, and the talent training mode will also have an impact on the effectiveness of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education. Through investigation, research and interviews, relevant personnel found that the talent training models of many vocational colleges have problems and cannot keep up with the needs of socioeconomic development and enterprises. Some vocational colleges still use the traditional teaching mode, in which teachers "arrange" teaching and students hardly participate actively. In this respect, it is mainly the result of the poor quality of the teaching staff in vocational colleges. Many teachers have almost no practical experience and ability in enterprises and do not know how to cultivate students' practical ability. In addition, the teaching technology and equipment were backward. The technology and equipment resources from more than ten years ago were still used and have not been updated and replaced. The new technology use methods have not been systematically trained. farther away. In addition, vocational colleges are not well off economically or even lack funds, so they have not been able to build good practical training bases, and it is difficult for students to have the opportunity to actually operate. Currently, what enterprises need is compound talent, but currently, there are no textbooks of this type in schools. The textbooks are all outdated, the professional disciplines are highly differentiated, and there are basically no integrated cross-professional textbooks, which places a great burden on teaching. Due to pressure, unreasonable class schedules appeared frequently. If after school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education, there is still no high-quality talent output, which will affect the effectiveness of the enterprise, it will greatly dampen the enthusiasm of enterprises for cooperation, and the enterprises may even withdraw from the cooperation, which is unfavorable for the long-term development of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education.

2.3 Analysis of influencing factors at the enterprise level

Enterprises are one of the most important subjects participating in school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education. Although the scale of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education in Haining is gradually increasing and development is actively promoted, it may still be in the initial stage of development, and the effect of cooperation will not be affected. Not significant.

Domestic and international studies all believe that enterprise scale and strength will affect the selection and effectiveness of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education. Small and medium-sized enterprises cannot match large enterprises in terms of talent reserves and technical strength. They very much hope that through school-enterprise cooperation, they can improve the ability of technical personnel and integrate and update their knowledge. Small and medium-sized enterprises pay attention to the issue of labor costs and pursue the goals of reducing costs and obtaining short-term profits. However, under the influence of technology preference, their original thinking of short-term goals is gradually changing, and they are setting more long-term goals and paying great attention to the accumulation of technology. and promotion. Although SMEs are limited in some areas and may not be able to provide that much help to vocational colleges, they hope very much to participate in the major setting of schools and to introduce enterprise standards into the talent training programs of vocational colleges. To create more internship opportunities for students. In this process, they are mutually beneficial and can obtain what they need and promote their own development.

Although large enterprises have abundant capital and technology, they have their own training institutions and have their own sets of programs for the training of enterprise talent. However, it is difficult for many enterprises to keep up with the speed of technological progress. They also realize that personal ability alone cannot keep up with the development of society. To update their information technology level, they are also willing to integrate into school-enterprise cooperation. In this process, they can rely on external forces, especially the scientific research capabilities of schoolteachers to carry out technology research and development, while integrating the processes and standards of enterprise training into the school's student training programs to achieve the docking of school-enterprise talent training programs.

When private enterprises participate in school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education, the first thing that comes to mind is the rewards they can obtain after participation, which is also in line with their essential attributes. Whether it can acquire new ideas and vitality and whether enterprises can obtain new technologies in the market, especially with the growing development of the concept of technology-biased technological progress, has placed more emphasis on seeking new technologies and new skills for enterprise development. This is a key factor for the development of an enterprise, which determines the survival of the enterprise. The cost of human resources training is also a critical factor. Most private enterprises are not very large and have limited funding capabilities and thus cannot afford the enormous amount of human training costs. However, school-enterprise cooperation can effectively reduce this cost. is one of the driving factors for their participation.

Social responsibility cannot affect the participation of private enterprises, while government responsibility is a key factor. Private enterprises themselves are not strong and can be said to be relatively weak. Therefore, when participating, they are more concerned with their own interests, and the pursuit of profit maximization is more important than the fulfillment of social responsibility. The appropriateness of the government's policies, the perfection of the institutional mechanisms, and the effective means of participation will directly affect the degree of participation of private enterprises. To obtain the maximum profit and high-quality skilled talent under the premise of saving costs, the content of cooperation will inevitably be limited. At this time, government support is urgently needed.

2.4 Analysis of Influencing Factors at the Level of Interest

For school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education, stakeholders have different classification methods. Here, the author believes that any group that has a direct or indirect relationship with vocational education school-enterprise cooperation is one of the scope of stakeholders. However, targeting those stakeholders can be based on the degree of influence. They are divided into different levels, and the specific distribution methods are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Classification of stakeholders in vocational education school-enterprise cooperation

Belong to level	Specific groups of stakeholders
Edge layer	Media, alumni associations, parents of students, etc.
Middle layer	Cooperation committees, industry enterprises
Core layer	Teachers, students, enterprises, government

In the development of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education, if all interest groups are to be taken into consideration, cooperation will become difficult. Therefore, we need to find a balance point to balance the distribution of interests, and this role falls to the core stakeholders. on the body. In the following text, the influencing factors are mainly analyzed from the perspective of core stakeholders.

2.4.1 Interest pursuits of enterprises—interest-based orientation

Acquire high-quality talent and advanced technologies to enhance the market competitiveness of enterprises. Haining's economy has entered a period of restructuring and development, the industrial structure is undergoing major adjustments, and the quality of talent demand is also constantly improving. Professional and technical personnel are particularly scarce in the "new normal" economic period. To solve this difficulty, many enterprises

will choose school-enterprise cooperation as a way to acquire high-quality talent. In this way, students will be exposed to the skills needed by the enterprise while they are in school, teachers will be more purposeful in the usual teaching process, striving to achieve the “zero distance” between the enterprise and the school, and they can enter the enterprise after graduation. Work more skillfully in the position. At the same time, the on-the-job employees of the enterprise can also enter school to acquire knowledge and improve their technical level to become even better workers in the new era. In-depth cooperation to achieve the integration of production, teaching and research is also the goal of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education. The school has strong scientific research capabilities and can provide great help to enterprises in technological innovation and product research and development and can compensate for the deficiencies of enterprises in technology research and development. The creation of a good technology R&D cooperation platform is conducive to the effective accumulation of technical knowledge and is of great significance for the enhancement of the core competitiveness of enterprises.

Enjoy preferential policies and increase popularity. The Haining government attaches great importance to school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education. To encourage enterprises to actively participate, the government has introduced some preferential policies. If an enterprise provides technical equipment or other resources to a vocational school in the training of students, it can enjoy preferential tax policies within a certain range; if the enterprise participates in the technology research and development of the vocational school, it can deduct part of the technology development fee. After receiving these preferential policies, the enterprises have reduced a large amount of their own expenditures. At present, participation in school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education is mainly concentrated in small and medium-sized enterprises. Their social status and reputation may not be at the same level as those of large enterprises, and their popularity is generally low. With the advent of the information age, enterprises also realize the importance of publicity, and the corporate image will affect their social status. A good way to increase the popularity of an enterprise is school-enterprise cooperation, and schools are also willing to act as this propagandist, which is also what they can combine.

2.4.2 Interest appeal of vocational colleges-quality-oriented orientation

Improve the quality of training while reducing the cost of education. Only high-quality technical skills talent can meet the demands of modern enterprises, vocational colleges have a higher probability of cultivating this kind of application-oriented talent, and the training mode is school-enterprise cooperation. Many vocational colleges hope to set up the training and practice base in the school so that the technical equipment of the enterprise can be introduced, and the enterprise will send excellent staff to teach the students, thus saving a number of lecture fees. After vocational colleges and enterprises share resources and jointly develop new technologies, they can promote the generation of school-enterprise cooperation. In addition, in the process of this cooperation, there will definitely be cultural integration, which is very helpful for the development of “dual-qualified” teachers in vocational colleges, and the use of enterprise resources to improve the practical ability of teachers and the increase in the transformation rate of achievements. Changing the teaching mode in the later stage was of great benefit and laid a good foundation. As front-line workers train students, teachers’ economic income will increase correspondingly after their abilities rise. They can also reflect social value on the basis of gaining happiness, all of which are brought about by school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education. As the objects of training, students can better integrate theory with practice and apply what they have learned. At the same time, they can also receive part of the allowance during the on-the-job internship, which reduces their financial burden.

Of course, increasing the popularity of vocational colleges is also a priority for them. In reality, when many students choose schools, they base their choices on the school’s brand and social reputation. Higher popularity will be conducive to the development of later enrollment. At the same time, we can eventually gain more collaborators, the care of the government, and the support of society.

2.4.3 The government’s interest pursuits—society-centered orientation

Create a good cooperative environment and promote local economic development. As a nonprofit organization, the government is also a public organization whose purpose is to serve society, create a better life for the general

public, and promote economic development. As the input department and the competent department of vocational education school-enterprise cooperation, the main interest pursuit is to increase labor productivity and promote the prosperity and development of the local economy through the use of personnel with advanced technical levels. Schools are the biggest exporters of the high-quality labor force. However, due to limitations of their own abilities, schools cannot provide all-round services. In this case, they must rely on external forces to jointly train students. The first choice of schools is enterprises. Therefore, to a certain extent, the government promotes the organic integration of vocational colleges and enterprises by creating a good cultural, economic and policy environment for the two and can play a bridging role in the middle.

From the above analysis, it can be seen that in the school-enterprise cooperation of vocational education, the interests of stakeholders are different. These interests can also be said to be important factors affecting school-enterprise cooperation because if these interests are satisfied, school-enterprise cooperation can proceed smoothly. Otherwise, it terminates. In terms of core stakeholders, enterprises have an interest-oriented orientation, vocational colleges have a quality-oriented orientation, and the government has a society-oriented orientation. Therefore, in the development of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education, ways must be found to satisfy their respective interests.

3. Countermeasures and suggestions for improving the effectiveness of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education

3.1 Give play to the leading role of the government in school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education

Strengthen top-level design and comprehensively plan and design school-enterprise cooperation programs. From the perspective of systems theory, the resources of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education are integrated from the overall perspective, and the participants and collaborators are coordinated. School-enterprise cooperation in vocational education is a strategic project that needs the support of a good organizational structure. It is recommended that government departments at all levels in Haining participate in the steering committee while clarifying the responsibility of each subject to implement each task. Through the top-level design of the government, the subsystems inside should be ensured to have the effect of $1+1>2$.

A decision-making system should be established to coordinate the relationship of interests. Vocational education school-enterprise cooperation involves the interests of multiple participants, and thus, they will face the problem of interest distribution. The interest relationship of all parties must be coordinated to achieve a balanced interest. First, it is necessary to ensure that all interested parties (such as enterprises, schools, regulatory departments, etc.) can participate in the negotiation of the distribution system so that the final decision-making reflects the common will of everyone. Second, the precondition for everyone to participate in the negotiation and discussion is to standardize the scope of the participants' rights and clarify their rights and obligations. Management functions should be redistributed to the education department, and vocational training rights should be redistributed to the industry management department.

3.2 Establish and improve the institutional framework for school-enterprise cooperation with the effective participation of industry associations

A collaboration mechanism for industry associations to establish vocational education school-enterprise cooperation has been established. Trade associations are very familiar with the development status of industries and enterprises. They are different from the market and the government. They are an independent subject as well as a collaborating subject of school-enterprise cooperation. They can make up for the deficiencies of the government in this regard and can also give full play to its resources. Allocate and establish a dialog and consultation mechanism with vocational colleges and enterprises. First, the educational function of trade associations must be played, and the organizational structures of trade associations should be improved. Second, the autonomy of trade associations should be enhanced. Because trade associations are independent organizations, to truly play their role and reflect the interest demands of industries and enterprises, the legal level

should be followed. The rights of trade associations shall be clearly stipulated so that they can play their roles under the protection of law.

An industry dialog and consultation mechanism shall be established. The effect of vocational education on economic growth is well known. The dialog and consultation mechanisms of industry associations should start at the national level, the management functions of the education department should be increased, and a steering committee should be established to be responsible for the cooperation and exchanges between the industry and vocational colleges. An online information platform is established to release the latest news of the industry. At the same time, a regular meeting system should be established to conduct more consultations, exchanges and matchmaking to help achieve school-enterprise integration.

3.3 Strengthen the legalization of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education

Accelerate the improvement of the legal system for school-enterprise cooperation. From the perspective of the current overall development speed, school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education The speed of development is faster than the promulgation of relevant laws and regulations; that is, the speed of the construction of laws and regulations cannot keep up with the speed of school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education. Economic development and the development of vocational education have produced major changes, and the external environment is also quite different from the previous environment. Many new issues have arisen that cannot be solved by the original laws and regulations. Therefore, the revision of these laws and regulations is imminent, and the establishment of a supporting new legal system is necessary. The first is to establish a cooperation system framework. Without a complete institutional guarantee, it will only be difficult to promote school-enterprise cooperation in vocational education and can only linger in the distance. A legal framework must be established around the interests of relevant subjects in participation. Second, accelerate the improvement of relevant subjects Vocational education laws and regulations The revision speed of the vocational education laws and regulations is based on the new situation of recent developments and the new problems encountered, as well as the market research and the summary analysis to supplement and improve the content of the vocational education laws and regulations.

We will focus on improving the enterprise participation system. The relevant systems of enterprises' participation in school-enterprise cooperation are extremely irregular. The main reason is that in the laws and regulations, the participating enterprises have not yet become the main units and have not stipulated their responsibilities; that is, the enterprises have not thus far been needed to bear any responsibility related to vocational education. Responsibilities related to school-enterprise cooperation Therefore, the first step is to establish the position of the enterprise in school-enterprise cooperation. The enterprise has the relevant responsibility for organizing vocational education and is also the main body of school-enterprise cooperation, so the legal status of the enterprise must be clarified. Second, the rights and responsibilities of enterprises should be clarified, internship posts should be provided, practical training places for vocational college students should be provided, labor responsibility should be assumed, vocational education and teaching should be participated, and excellent enterprise employees should be sent to help improve teaching quality in vocational colleges. Of course, there will be corresponding rights, such as the right to give priority to the selection of outstanding students to work in enterprises and the right to assess students.

3.4 Strengthen the correlation between vocational education and the interests of cooperative enterprises

The cultivation of technical and skilled personnel is the purpose of higher vocational education, which provides a large number of skilled personnel for production management and service frontlines every year. The way to train talent is the integration of production and education into school-enterprise cooperation. This way can enable the participants to win-win each other. . Regrettably, there are still problems in the cooperation concept. The school and the enterprise cannot analyze it from the perspective of behavioral decision-making. As a result, the quality of school-enterprise cooperation for the integration of industry and education has not been very high. Of course, to carry out in-depth and quality school-enterprise cooperation on the integration of industry and education, one of the important factors is the establishment of a close interest relationship. In the context of a market economy, an important reason for enterprises to participate in school-enterprise cooperation is the drive

of interests because the nature of the enterprises determines their motivations for participation. It is impossible for enterprises to participate solely on the basis of their enthusiasm for education or the pressure of public opinion at the moral level. School-enterprise cooperation. Of course, it is not excluded that a small number of companies participate in school-enterprise cooperation for public welfare purposes, but this behavior will not last for too long. To this end, in the school-enterprise cooperation process of the integration of industry and education in higher vocational education, we must emphatically highlight the subject awareness of enterprises and increase their enthusiasm for participation. The government will give certain preferential policies to those enterprises that have played a leading and demonstration role to attract more enterprises. More enterprises have participated in school-enterprise cooperation on the integration of production and education in higher vocational colleges.

Data availability: The authors have included all the relevant data and the source of freely available data in the manuscript.

Declarations: Ethics approval No prior ethical approval was necessary for the study.

Consent to participate: No human subjects included in the study. Consent not required.

Consent to publication: Not applicable.

Competing interests: The authors declare no competing interests.

Funding: This paper was supported by the Zhejiang provincial education scientific planning project (2023SCG239).

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